

ON THE GEOPHYSICAL INPUT IN ASSESING SPACE WEATHER HAZARD INDUCED BY GEOMAGNETIC STORMS (GICS)

Venera Dobrica and Crisan Demetrescu

Institute of Geodynamics, Romanian Academy, venera@geodin.ro

The external geomagnetic field, arising from the magnetospheric and ionospheric current systems, developed at the interaction of solar wind and heliospheric magnetic field with the Earth's magnetic field, especially geomagnetic storms, might induce hazardous response as shown by the surface electric field, the geophysical input in assessing ground space weather impact of geomagnetically induced currents (GICs). In this study, several space weather events are analyzed both from point of view of solar cause and from point of view of near-Earth/ground effects. The surface electric field, induced by the variable magnetic field of geomagnetic storms, is determined based on the geomagnetic field recordings and on information regarding the underground electric conductivity. An example of the variable magnetic field recorded during September 6-12, 2017, including the geomagnetic storm September 8, 2017, at certain European geomagnetic observatories, together with geomagnetic indices SYM-H, AE and PC, which describe, respectively, magnetospheric, ionospheric and polar cap current systems, is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 The X component of the geomagnetic field during a geomagnetic storm on September 8, 2017, at geomagnetic observatories, and geomagnetic indices SYM-H, AE and PC

The surface geoelectric field has been calculated using the plane wave model of Viljanen and Pirjola (1989). Assuming that the horizontal electric field (E_x, E_y) produced by the variable geomagnetic field (B_x, B_y) through the impedance $Z(\omega)$ of the Earth's interior is given by:

$$E_x(\omega) = \frac{Z(\omega)}{\mu_0} B_y(\omega), E_y(\omega) = \frac{Z(\omega)}{\mu_0} B_x(\omega),$$

for a half-space Earth of conductivity σ , the surface electric field is rewritten by

$$E_y(t) = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi\mu_0\sigma}} \int_{-\infty}^t \frac{g_x(u)}{\sqrt{t-u}} du,$$

where g is the time derivative of the field B . Developing a Matlab code, the integral has been transformed in a sum that allowed calculating 1-minute values of the electric field E . For underground electric conductivity we used the model of Adam et al. (2012).

The geographical distribution of the maximum surface geoelectric field at local (Romania) and continental (Europe) scales for certain geomagnetic storms is presented. In Fig. 2 the distribution of E_{max} over Europe for two geomagnetic storms (March 17, 2015 with $Dst = -223$ nT, and September 8, 2017 with $Dst = -124$ nT) is given as an example.

Fig . 2 Maximum intensity of the surface geoelectric field induced by the geomagnetic storms of March 17, 2015 (left) and September 8, 2017 (right)

Concluding remarks

- storms differ from each other primarily because of interacting solar wind conditions and state of magnetosphere
- the disturbance in X is 2-3 times larger at northern latitudes than at mid and southern latitudes for both geomagnetic storms; its amplitude and morphology is a result of the evolution of the two main direct sources of the geomagnetic activity: the magnetospheric ring current & the auroral ionospheric electrojets;

- the amplitude of the geoelectric field is of the order of tenths of V/km, for both geomagnetic storms, in case of SUA (45°N), and of 0.5-1 V/km, for September 2017 and of 1-2 V/km, for March 2015 geomagnetic storms, in case of UPS (60°N);
- the maximum E value is not reached at the same moment at all observatories and its orientation depends on that moment of the storm development. Probable cause: local electric structure of the underground;
- the geoelectric hazard (GICs) is significant above the 50°N (S) geomagnetic latitude.

References

- Adam A., Pracser E., Wesztergom V. (2012). Estimation of the electric resistivity distribution (EURHOM) in the European lithosphere in the frame of the EURISGIC WP2 project. *Acta Geod. Geoph. Hung.*, 47, pp 377-387
- Viljanen A., Pirjola R. (1989). Statistics on geomagnetically-induced currents in the Finnish 400 kV Power system based on recordings of geomagnetic variations. *J. Geomag. Geoelectr.*, 41, pp 411-420